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METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION FOR ESTIMATION OF EPERISONE HYDROCHLORIDE AS API AND IN PHARMACEUTICAL PREPARATION BY KINETIC SPECTROSCOPY

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ABSTRACT

A simple and sensitive kinetic spectrophotometric method has been successfully developed for the determination of Eperisone hydrochloride based on its oxidation using potassium permanganate in alkaline medium. The rate of change of reaction was recorded at 603.5 nm. The different experimental parameters were studied and optimized. 5 minutes and 3 minutes were chosen for the development of initial rate and fixed time method respectively. Calibration curve was found to be linear over the concentration range of 15-35 µg/ml for initial rate method and 15-30 µg/ml for fixed time method. The method was applied for estimation of eperisone hydrochloride in RAPISONE (marketed by Abbott, Maharashtra). The assay results were found to be 99.93% ± 0.05 and 99.42% ± 0.05 by initial rate and fixed time method. RSD values were found to be ≤2%. The results were validated as per the ICH guidelines.

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INTRODUCTION:

Eperisone hydrochloride, an antispasmodic drug, sold in south-east asia.¹ It is a piperidinopropiophenone analogue and its structure is shown in figure 1. It acts on skeletal muscles and vascular smooth muscles, and demonstrates reduction of myotonia, improvement of circulation, and suppression of pain reflex.² Kinetic spectrophotometric methods have regained interest in recent past due to its specific advantages as well as the improved capabilities of the modern instrument.³⁻⁵ LC-ESI-MS⁶ and GC-MS^{7, 8} and HPLC^{9, 10} methods were proposed for determination of eperisone hydrochloride in biological fluids. Various methods were proposed for estimation of degradation products.¹¹ Potentiometry is the official method in Japanese Pharmacopeia¹². Kinetic spectrophotometric method has not been reported so far in any literature. The objective of the research is to develop and validate kinetic spectrophotometric method for the estimation of drug for routine analysis in bulk and tablet dosage form.

MATERIALS AND METHOD:

Double distilled water was used as solvent for analysis. 6×10^{-3} M of potassium permanganate (KMnO₄) (LOBA CHEMIE, India) and 1 M of sodium hydroxide (NaOH) (LOBA CHEMIE, India) were prepared in distilled water. Shimadzu UV-1800 model (with a wavelength accuracy of 0.3 nm) and one cm matched quartz cells was used for spectral measurements with spectral band width one nm. Glasswares (manufactured by Borosil) were used throughout the research. They were washed and dried at the end of each day's work. Weighing was done on electronic balance (GR-200, A& D Company). Pure drug of eperisone hydrochloride was obtained as gift sample from Sun Pharma Industries, Mumbai. Tablets of brand name RAPISONE (Batch no.-AME-008B), marketed by Abbott, Maharashtra and SKELACT (Batch no.-ADJ-0729), marketed by Sun Pharma Industries, Mumbai were procured from local pharmacy.

Preparation of Standard stock solution

Stock solution for method development: 100 mg of Eperisone hydrochloride was accurately weighed and transferred to 100 ml volumetric flask, dissolved in doubly distilled water and the volume was made upto 100 ml with the same. The final solution contained 1000 µg/ml of Eperisone hydrochloride solution.

Stock solution for stoichiometric determination: 177.5 mg of Eperisone hydrochloride was accurately weighed and transferred to 10 ml volumetric flask, dissolved in doubly distilled water and the volume was made upto 10 ml with the same. The final solution contained 17750 µg per ml of Eperisone hydrochloride solution.

Preparation of sample solution of pharmaceutical tablets

20 tablets were weighed and triturated well. A quantity of powder equivalent to 50 mg of drug was transferred to 100 ml volumetric flask and mixed with 25 ml of double distilled water and solution was sonicated for 15 min.. The volume was finally made up to 100 ml with double distilled water. The solution was filtered through Whatmann filter paper no. 42. The filtrate was diluted with water to obtain working concentration in the range of 15- 25 µg/ml for the drug.

PROCEDURE:

Initial rate method: A series of dilutions (150–350 µg/ml) was prepared by pipetting out different aliquots of standard stock solution of Eperisone hydrochloride into a series of 10 ml volumetric flask. At the time of observation, 1.6 ml of sodium hydroxide solution (1 M) was added followed by 2.0 ml of potassium permanganate solution (6×10^{-3} M) to each flask and then diluted to the volume with double-distilled water.

The content of mixture of each flask was mixed well and the increase in absorbance at 603.5 nm was recorded as a function of time for 15 min. against reagent blank treated similarly.

Fixed time method: In this method, the absorbance was recorded accurately at preselected time of 3, 6, 9, 12 and 15 min. against reagent blank treated similarly.

Data acquisition:

The initial rate of reaction at different concentration was obtained from the slope of tangent to the absorbance time curve (at 5 min.). A calibration curve was plotted between log of the initial rate of the reaction (Log dA/dt) against log of the concentration. The calibration graphs were also constructed for fixed time by plotting the absorbance against concentration of the drug at a preselected fixed time of 3 min. The concentration of the drug was determined from calibration curve.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Optimization of the Kinetic parameters:

Potassium permanganate has been used as an oxidimetric analytical reagent for determination of Eperisone hydrochloride. The heptavalent manganese ion changes to the green color (Mn VI), while in neutral and acidic medium, the permanganate is further reduced to colorless (Mn II). This behavior of permanganate was the basis for its uses in development of spectrophotometric method. The absorption spectrum of aqueous potassium permanganate solution in alkaline medium exhibited an absorption band at 526 nm. The additions of Eperisone hydrochloride to this solution produce a new characteristic band at 603.5 nm. The absorption spectra are shown in figure 2. This band is due to formation of manganate ion, which resulted from the oxidation of Eperisone hydrochloride by potassium permanganate in alkaline medium. The intensity of the color increased with time; therefore a kinetically based method was developed for determination of Eperisone hydrochloride in their pharmaceutical dosage formulations.

Effect of potassium permanganate concentration

The absorbance increases substantially with increasing the concentration of potassium permanganate as shown in figure 3. Maximum absorbance was obtained when 2.0 ml of 0.006 M of potassium permanganate was used. Thus, the adoption of 2 ml of potassium permanganate in the final solution proved to be adequate for the maximum concentration of Eperisone hydrochloride used in determination process (final concentration was 0.0012 M).

Effect of sodium hydroxide concentration

Maximum absorption was obtained when 1.6 ml of 1 M NaOH was used. Over this volume no deliberate change in absorbance could be detected. So 1.6 ml of 1 M of NaOH was used as an optimum value as shown in figure 4.

Effect of temperature

At room temperature the reaction rate increased substantially with time. Although heating the solution was found to increase the rate of the reaction but MnO_2 was precipitated out rapidly. Therefore room temperature was selected as the optimum temperature.

Stoichiometry and reaction mechanism^{13, 14}

The stoichiometric ratio between potassium permanganate and Eperisone hydrochloride was determined by Job's method and was found to be 4:1. Corrected Job's plot is shown in figure 5. Eperisone hydrochloride was

found to be susceptible for oxidation with alkaline potassium permanganate producing a green color peaking at 603.5 nm.

Kinetics of the reaction:

Under the optimum conditions, the absorbance time curves of Eperisone hydrochloride with potassium permanganate reagent were constructed in figure 6, 7). The initial rate of the reaction was determined from the slope of tangents of the absorption time curves. The order of the reaction with respect to permanganate was determined by studying the reaction at different concentrations of permanganate with fixed concentration of investigated Eperisone hydrochloride. The plot of initial rate ($\Delta A/\Delta t$) against initial absorbance was linear passing through origin indicating that the initial order of the reaction with respect to permanganate was 1 as shown in figure 8.

The order with respect to investigated Eperisone hydrochloride was evaluated by measuring the rate of the reaction at several concentrations of Eperisone hydrochloride at a fixed concentration of permanganate reagent, as shown in figure 9. This was done by plotting the logarithm of initial rate of the reaction versus logarithm of molar concentration of investigated Eperisone hydrochloride and was found to be approximately 1, as shown in figure 10. However under the optimized experimental conditions, the concentrations of Eperisone hydrochloride were determined using relative excess amount of potassium permanganate and sodium hydroxide solutions. Therefore pseudo-zero-order conditions were obtained with respect to their concentrations.

Quantitation methods

Initial rate method

Initial rate of reaction would follow pseudo-first order and were found to follow equation (1).

$$V = dA/dt = K' C^n \quad (1)$$

Where V is the reaction rate, A is absorbance, t is the measuring time, K' is the pseudo-first order rate constant, C is the molar concentration and n is the order of the reaction. The logarithmic form of the reaction is shown in equation (2).

$$\text{Log } v = \text{Log } \frac{\Delta A}{\Delta t} = \text{Log } K' + n \text{Log } C \quad (2)$$

Regression analysis using the method of least square was performed to evaluate the slopes, intercepts, and correlation coefficient. The analytical parameters and results of regression analysis are given in Table 1. The value of n (≈ 1) in the regression equation confirmed that the reaction of Eperisone hydrochloride with the potassium permanganate was pseudo-first-order with respect to Eperisone hydrochloride concentration. The limits of detection (LOD) were calculated and results obtained confirmed good sensitivity of the proposed method and consequently their capabilities to determine low amount of Eperisone hydrochloride.

Fixed time method

In this method, the absorbance of the reaction solution containing varying amount of Eperisone HCl was measured at preselected fixed time. Calibration plots of absorbance versus the concentration of the drug at fixed time were established as shown in figure 11. The regression equation, correlation coefficients, and detection limits are given in Table 2. The lowest detection limit was obtained at fixed time of 6 min. However, the fixed time of 3 min. showed a wider concentration range for quantification.

Validation of Proposed Methods¹⁵⁻¹⁸

Specificity

Since the proposed method was performed in visible range away from the UV- absorption region, very minor changes in the absorbance values was seen during the time duration.

Linearity

Linearity data are studied for both methods and reported in Table 1 and 2.

Table 1: Table representing analytical parameters for the initial rate method for determination of eperisone hydrochloride with alkaline potassium permanganate ($\Delta t = 300$ sec)

Method	Linearity	Log K	Slope (n)	r^2	LOD	LOQ
Initial rate	15-30 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	0.998	0.808	0.998	0.467327	1.416142

Table 2: Table representing analytical parameters for the fixed time method for determination of eperisone hydrochloride with alkaline potassium permanganate

Reaction time (sec)	Linearity range (ppm)	Intercept	S.D.	Slope	S.D.	r^2	LOD	LOQ
180	15-35	0.035	0.006	0.029	0.000	0.998	0.656	1.991
360	15-30	0.105	0.001	0.033	0.001	0.999	0.152	0.462
540	15-25	0.11	0.019	0.035	0.001	0.998	1.814	5.498
720	15-20	0.07	0.021	0.087	0.008	1	0.792	2.401
900	15-20	0.1	0.012	0.033	0.000	1	1.154	3.499

Table 3: Data representing evaluation of accuracy of the analytical procedure using Initial Rate method

S. no.	Amount of tablet added ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Amount of sol ⁿ added ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Amount of sol ⁿ added ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Log dA/dt (Mean)	Amount found ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery S.D.	% \pm % RSD
1.	10	10	10	-2.851	19.985	99.929	100.54 \pm 0.77	0.767
2.	10	15	15	-2.872	25.074	100.299		

3.	10	20	-2.775	30.423	101.411
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Table 4: Data representing evaluation of accuracy of the analytical procedure using fixed time method

S. no.	Amount of tablet added ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Amount of sol ⁿ added ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Mean Abs	Amount found ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery S.D.	% \pm	% RSD
1.	10	10	0.628	19.883	99.418	99.229 0.1636	\pm	0.165
2.	10	15	0.753	24.780	99.122			
3.	10	20	0.892	29.744	99.148			

Table 5: Data showing intraday precision analysis for initial rate method

Conc. ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Time	Conc. Found ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Mean \pm S.D.	% RSD
20	10 a.m.	20	20.024 \pm 0.042	0.211
	12 p.m.	20.073		
	2 p.m.	20		
25	10 a.m.	25	25.0 \pm 0	0
	12 p.m.	25		
	2 p.m.	25		
30	10 a.m.	30	30.006 \pm 0.010	0.033
	12 p.m.	30		
	2 p.m.	30.017		
Mean %RSD				0.081

Accuracy

Accuracy studies for initial rate and fixed time method are reported in table 3 and 4. The results of mean of % recovery were found to be 100.54% \pm 0.77 by initial rate and 99.229% \pm 0.163 by fixed time method. % RSD were found to be 0.767% and 0.165% for initial rate and fixed time method respectively. As the values were less than 2% so the proposed method was found to be accurate.

Precision

The precision data of initial rate and fixed time method are represented in table 5-8. The results showed %R.S.D of 0.081% and 0.180% for initial rate method and 0.777% and 0.938% for fixed time method. As the values were found to be less than 2% it can be concluded that the analytical technique had a good precision.

Detection and Quantification limits

The values are reported in table 1 and 2.

Table 6: Data showing interday analysis for initial rate method

Conc. ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Day	Conc. Found ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Mean \pm S.D.	% RSD
20	Day I	20.0	20.017 \pm 0.015	0.076
	Day II	20.03		
	Day III	20.02		
25	Day I	25.0	25.056 \pm 0.061	0.246
	Day II	25.06		
	Day III	25.18		
30	Day I	30.0	30.070 \pm 0.06	0.220
	Day II	30.08		
	Day III	30.13		
Mean %RSD				0.180

Figure 1: Chemical structure of Eperisone hydrochloride

Figure 2: Absorption spectra of (A) Eperisone hydrochloride (20 µg/ml); (B) alkaline potassium permanganate (6×10^{-3} M) and (C) the reaction product.

Figure 3: Effect of potassium permanganate on the reaction between the investigated Eperisone hydrochloride (20 µg/ml) and alkaline potassium permanganate.

Figure 4: Effect of sodium hydroxide concentration (1 M) on the reaction between Eperisone hydrochloride (20 µg/ml) and alkaline potassium permanganate.

Figure 5: Job's plots of continuous variation between potassium permanganate and Eperisone hydrochloride.

Figure 6: Figure representing change in absorbance with respect to time as recorded by UV in Kinetics mode.

Figure 7: Absorption versus time for the reaction between Eperisone hydrochloride (6.76×10^{-5} M) and KMnO_4 (0.3 to 1.8×10^{-3} M).

APPLICATION OF THE PROPOSED METHOD:

The initial rate and fixed time method of the proposed kinetic spectrophotometric methods were applied for determining Eperisone HCl on commercial pharmaceutical tablets. The tablet content was computed from its corresponding regression equations. The obtained mean recovery values of the labeled amounts were $99.93\% \pm 0.05$ and $99.41\% \pm 0.04$. The data are reported in Table 9 and 10.

Table 7: Data showing intraday precision analysis for fixed time method

Conc. ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Time	Conc. Found ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Mean \pm S.D.	% RSD
20	10 a.m.	20		
	12 p.m.	19.68	19.89 ± 0.18	0.92
	2 p.m.	20		
25	10 a.m.	25		
	12 p.m.	24.67	24.78 ± 0.19	0.76
	2 p.m.	24.67		
30	10 a.m.	30		
	12 p.m.	29.67	29.89 ± 0.19	0.64
	2 p.m.	30		
Mean % RSD				0.777

Table 8: Data showing interday analysis for Eperisone hydrochloride

Conc. ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Day	Conc. Found ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Mean \pm S.D.	% RSD
20	Day I	20		
	Day II	19.81	19.83 \pm 0.157	0.805
	Day III	19.68		
Day I	25			
25	Day II	24.70	24.76 \pm 0.205	0.829
	Day III	24.60		
	Day I	30		
30	Day II	29.66	29.65 \pm 0.35	1.180
	Day III	29.30		
Mean % RSD				0.938

Table 9: Estimation of Eperisone hydrochloride in tablet by proposed Initial rate method

Brand name	Label claim (mg)	Log dA/dt	Conc. Found (mg)	Amt. found in per Tablet (% Assay)
Rapisone	50 mg	-2.859	20.036	49.965 mg (99.93% \pm 0.05)
		-2.844	19.935	
		-2.852	19.985	
Mean			19.98582	

Table 10: Estimation of Eperisone hydrochloride in tablet by proposed fixed time method

Brand name	Label claim (mg)	Log dA/dt	Conc. Found (mg)	Amt. found in per Tablet (% Assay)
RAPISONE	50 mg	0.628	19.936	49.708 mg (99.42% \pm 0.05)
		0.625	19.841	
		0.626	19.873	
Mean			19.883	

Figure 8: Plot of initial rate (dA/dt, where t= 300 s) v/s initial absorbance A.

Figure 9: Absorption versus time for the reaction between Eperisone hydrochloride (5.07 to 11.8×10^{-5} M) and KMnO_4 (1.2×10^{-4} M).

Figure 10: Plot of log initial rate (dA/dt, where t= 300 s) v/s Log concentration.

Figure 11: Calibration plot of absorbance versus the concentration of Eperisone hydrochloride at preselected fixed time of 3 min.

CONCLUSION:

The present study describes a simple and sensitive kinetic spectrophotometric method for determination of Eperisone HCl in bulk as well as tablet dosage forms, This method has been used in the past for the elemental analysis and detection of bio-molecules in biological fluids (like enzymes). Initial rate and fixed time methods were found to be sensitive enough for analysis of lower amount of the drug. The results of accuracy, precision and assay were in good agreement with the threshold limits of validation parameters as per ICH guidelines. Furthermore, the proposed method does not require expensive instruments and critical analytical reagents. These advantages give the developed methods a great value and encourage its application to analyze Eperisone HCl in quality control laboratories.

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